

Applications of Nanotechnology in Fruits and Vegetables

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Abstract—Nanotechnology is one of the emerging technique of preservation not only in food industry but in other fields we are aware of Various new and innovative applications about nanotechnology and nanoscience has been developed in the food industry. Those applications are utilized for food sector, agriculture, horticulture, food science namely food production, food processing, nano-packaging, nanosensors and fruits and vegetable packaging. Due to the perishable natures, fruits and vegetables can not be stored in natural conditions for long period of time. Conventional methods are also applicable for preserving fruits and vegetables but because of few limitations like high cost, unsatisfactory results, or poor shelf life improvement are not preferred. Nanotechnology has not reported any harmful effects till now hence it can be effectively utilized in the food industry. Also, the shelf life of fruits and vegetables can be effectively improved by utilization of nanotechnology. Providing safe and sufficient food to the customers, reducing the post harvest wastages and the losses during production has become the native aim of food manufacturers. To reduce the losses and wastages is the major challenge before food industries which has a best solution named nanotechnology or nano-packaging. Nanomaterials are the core of the nanotechnology. Nanomaterials plays an important role in food preservation due to its unique characteristic of developing enumerous ability to increase the physical properties of the food as well as packaging materials. Nanopacking or nano-packaging is useful for lowering the relative humidity, oxygen transmission rate and water vapor transmission rate. Hence, it consequently improves the shelf life of the product. This review gives the idea about overall scope and demand of nanotechnology in the packaging sector to improve shelf lives of the products and liase for safety and quality of the food products.

Index Terms—Nanotechnology, Nanoparticles, Nanocoating, Fruits and vegetables, Food preservation, Nanolaminates, Nanofood, Nanosensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is the scientific technique in which the materials having structure less than 100 nanometer (nm) are produced or utilized. This technique shows a simulative effect when combined with already existing techniques because nanotechnology is the new, emerging technology. The role of the nanotechnology starts from production, manufacturing up to distribution in the food industry. Nanofood are the food that is created using nanotechnology techniques while cultivation, manufacturing, packaging. The term nanotechnology is not limited to only foods. Nanotechnology is helpful for revolutionize the many other existing techniques and industrial sectors. It is applicable for the fields like pharmaceuticals, food safety, environmental science, health care, communication technology etc. The future demands for the innovative and new products and processes. Nanotechnology can be the one of the emerging and useful technique in the food sector. Today, nanotech R&D of food packaging and the monitoring of nanotech food packaging is a major focus in the food industry. (Wesley et al., 2014). Nanotechnology applications are also used to detect the presence of the bacteria in the packaging. Nano-packaging improves the safety and quality of the products by raising barrier properties of the packaging materials. The types of nanomaterials or nanoparticles can be used such as natural nanoparticles which can be eaten safely and does not cause harmful effects on human health.

II. HISTORY OF PACKAGING

Food packaging has evolved from simply a container to hold food to something today that can play an active role in food quality. (Risch, 2009) Packaging material has three primary functions of providing protection, utility, and communication in three different environments. The environments are physical, atmospheric and human. The goal is to optimize a package to provide for all three functions especially in all three environments. (Risch, 2009). Many revolutions are happening in the industries. Hence, it is important to develop manufacturing processes and introduce new materials and techniques. The history of food packaging began 3500 years ago in Egypt glass and continued with mulberry bark containers in china and napoleon's pushed for canned foods. In the history of metal packaging the first packaged material used was metal printed box in 1866 in USA. Later on, the first aluminum canned food came in 1959. Nowadays food packaging has revolutionized in many ways. Nanotechnology or nano-packaging is one of the innovative and new technique has been introduced in food packaging for its safety purpose.

III. APPLICATIONS OF NANOTECHNOLOGY IN FOOD INDUSTRY

Nanotechnology is potentially used in the field of food and agriculture. Nanotechnology is important to the food science, food packaging, food preservation, science and engineering of agriculture. Nanotechnology is the technique or tool used to achieve advancements in the food industries. Examples are as follows:

- Utilization of nanotechnology increases the safety measures in food manufacturing, processing, packaging and distribution.
- Can be used to sense, detect and provide warning about possible problems during processing.
- Utilized to increase the flavor and introduce antibacterial nanoparticles into food.
- Most probably nanotechnology is utilized to enhance the shelf life of the food.
- For safety packaging of food, nanobarcodes are used and it also monitors distribution of food products.
- To increase nutritional components into the food, nanosupplements can be easily incorporated by this technique.
- The IP naosensors has huge benefit in food industry which is useful for monitoring the food in all its phases (production, processing, packaging, distribution).

FIGURE 1: Application matrix of nanotechnology in food science and technology. (Fuertes et al., 2016).

IV. NANOTECHNOLOGY IN FRUITS AND VEGETABLES

Biopreservation is one of the great challenges for food industry. For biopreservation food must be packed or coated with suitable material. Coating or prevention films can be directly applied to the food products. Food products requires different preservation techniques according to their nature. Fruits and vegetable are perishable in nature, they have less shelf life because of their high oxygen and water vapor transmission rate. Hence, the shelf life of the fruits and vegetables passes away from the moment of picking the fruits or vegetable, its semi-processing and then finally no

longer acceptable for consumers. The main factors for the deterioration of the fresh fruits and vegetables are as follows:

- Microbial load- Growth and activities of micro-organisms, principally bacteria, yeasts and moulds.
- Activities of enzymes present in fruits and vegetables (Polyphenoloxidase, Peroxidase, Lipoxygenases).
- Temperatures, both heat and cold
- Time
- Insects and rodents

Deterioration of fruits and vegetables can be caused by various factors like cutting, freezing, desiccating, microbial growth, contact with already spoiled food, microbial spoilage etc. Most of the times the post harvest losses are occurs in the fruits and vegetables. Post harvest losses are mainly caused due to the mechanical, pathological or environmental factors. Mechanical damage of fruits and vegetables is a result of careless handling during harvesting, packaging, transportation and storage. Post harvest losses can be reduced by proper activities of harvesting, transportation and storage. Certain environmental factors are responsible for the pathogenic damages of fruits and vegetables. Those factors include temperature, relative humidity, oxygen balance. The common that are responsible for rots in vegetables and fruits are fungi such as *Altenia*, *Rhizopus*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium* etc. Proper packaging of fresh or semi-processed fruits and vegetables is very necessary. The environmental factors responsible for degradation of fruits and vegetables are light, oxygen, water activity, temperature.

1. NANOCOATING

Nanocoating is the thin layer of <1-100 nm thick built up onto surfaces. Nanocoating are formed from a single or multiple application of coating materials nanocoating helps to provide barriers against the foreign materials and other substances. nanocoating not only prolong shelf life but also provides additional nutrients. It is a time-saving technique used for coating of perishable produce like fruits and vegetables Due to coating the pores present on skin which are responsible for water loss are blocked. Wax coating is used for many fruits such as citrus, tomato, apple etc. Wax coating is basically used for improving the external appearance of the food and reduce the rate of oxygen and water vapor transmission. Food grade waxes are used for the fruits.

FIGURE 2: Nanocoated fruits and vegetables (Raghav et al., 2016)

2. NANOLAMINATES

Nanolaminates are also the thin films. These are formed by two or more layers of food grade materials. Different antimicrobials, antioxidants, antibrowning agents can be incorporated into the films. These agents help to increase the shelf life of the product. Different types of substances can be used to create layers such as polysaccharides, phospholipids. Fresh fruits and vegetables have high moisture content hence, there is high biological activities. Nanolaminates are used in the fruits and vegetables to control the biological activity and improve the shelf life. Nanolaminates are very useful to reduce post harvest losses in fruits and vegetables such as tomato. The use of edible laminates is mainly based on the post harvest techniques in agriculture to solve problems of microbial growth during transportation and storage.

3. NANOSENSORS

Nanosensors are the devices used for determining the condition of the food products. Nanosensors improves the problems of food packaging. Nanosensors gives the surety to the consumers about the products they are purchasing. Nanosensors helps to provide fresh and safe food to the consumers. Presence of nanosensors helps to reduce frequency of food borne illness which is useful to maintain food safety. Nanosensors are nothing but the nanoparticles which are having characteristics of pathogen detection. Nanosensors are the mechanical or chemical sensors that are used to detect the physical or chemical parameters . Nanosensors are used in food industries to achieve desired level of sensitivity. The advantages of nanosensors over the conventional sensors is its improved sensitivity and specificity.

FIGURE 3: Application of nanomaterials (Nanosensors) in different fields (Kumar et al., 2017).

4. NANOBIOSENSORS-

Nanobiosensors are mainly used in the food as well as pharmaceutical industries.

- Multi-enzymatic sensors are used in food industry for sucrose determination.
- Glutamate sensors are used to measure glutamate concentration in the production of monosodium glutamate.
- Ethanol sensors are the microbial sensors to measure ethanol concentration in the process of alcohol fermentation,

V. ACTIVE PACKAGING

Active packaging is a technique of incorporating active compounds into the matrix of commonly used packaging materials . Methods like immobilization, coating, sachets or pads are used for the incorporation. Active packaging changes the condition of food. The active packaging changes the condition of the food which is packed inside the packaging material. Active packaging includes two major parts :

1. NANO ANTIMICROBIAL PACKAGING
2. OXYGEN SCAVENGING MATERIALS

- 1) Nano-based antimicrobial packaging and food contact materials-
According to the the changes in the microbial population, humidity, and many other changing conditions, the packaging material and food contact materials incorporate antimicrobial nanoparticles, so that packaging itself act as an antimicrobial. The most common nanoparticles used are nano zinc oxide and nano chlorine oxide and nano magnesium oxide, nano copper oxide and nano titanium oxide and carbon nanotubes are predicted for future use in antimicrobial food packaging.

FIGURE 4:Nano antimicrobial food packaging

2) Oxygen scavenging material-

Food deterioration due to indirect contact of oxygen which is basically includes food spoilage by aerobic type of microorganisms. Oxygen scavengers are available commercially in the form of sachets which contains the metallic or inorganic reducing agents like iron oxide, ferrous carbonate etc.

VI. INTELLIGENT PACKAGING

Food safety is the main objective of food laws. Quality control in the food products is basically maintained by physical, sensory attributes, microbial safety of the food and nutritional value of the food. Intelligent packaging is a type of smart packaging which extends the communication function of traditional food packaging.

• INDICATORS USED IN INTELLIGENT PACKAGING-

1. Time and temperature indicators. These indicators are used to indicate the exposure to excessive temperature. It also monitors the condition of food product at the time of production. These sensors monitor the changes in the temperatures in which the products are exposed. These sensors indicate the irreversible changes like physical characteristics, shape, color according to the temperature.
2. Freshness indicators. Freshness indicators are commercially used in intelligent packaging to indicate the quality of the product. Freshness indicators are centered on color change of the indicator tag due to presence of spoilage causing microorganisms.
3. Leakage indicators or integrity indicators. Leakage indicators are attached to the packaging to detect the integrity of the package throughout the production and distribution.

VII. FUTURE OF NANOTECHNOLOGY IN FOOD PACKAGING

Nanotechnology is an emerging field having lots of applications in food science and technology. Nanotechnology also plays an important role in the packaging process. The use of nanotechnology in food packaging improves physical barrier properties, antimicrobial properties that improves the shelf life of the product. The use of nanotechnology in food packaging helps to reduce the gas and moisture exchange. During food processing, nanoparticles have been applied to improve nutritional quality, flow properties, flavor, color, and stability or to increase shelf life. (Wesley et al., 2014). The potential use of the nanotechnology is in functional foods.

Nanotechnology is also utilized to design nutraceuticals, nutritional supplements. The nanomaterials are used for nano encapsulation containing nanosized ingredients such as vitamins, antioxidants, preservatives, additives etc. These are used to enhance taste, flavor, and shelf life of the food products. Nanoencapsulation is one of the emerging technique which is potentially used to protect sensitive food ingredients from various environmental factors. The interest

in the nanotechnology is increasing day by day. And along with the need of food safety and quality, nanotechnology in food packaging is on high demand nowadays. Nanotechnology will have benefit in all the type of industries. Food science and technology is the field in which nanotechnology will play an important role in future. Food safety is the main perspective of food manufacturers, which can be achieved by the nanotechnology. As the nanotechnology is helpful in-

1. Increasing the security during manufacturing, processing and packaging.
2. Provides the sensors which is useful to detect the problems and provides early warnings.
3. Nanopackages are used to influence shelf life, texture and flavor of the products.
4. Different indicators can be used to detect the leakages, food pathogens, extension in temperature etc.
5. Nanoencapsulation is the technique used to enhance nutritional content by incorporating vitamins, minerals etc.

VIII. NANOTOXICOLOGY

The evaluation in nanotechnology is one of the major advantages in different fields and human lives. But the manipulation of nanoparticles can also have diverse effects in manufacturing, health, technology, pharmaceutical industry etc. Nanoparticles has the higher ability to travel through organisms than higher materials. Nanotoxicology is nothing but the adverse effects that are caused due to nanoparticles. It also includes the adverse effects that are caused due to consumption of nanofoods.

1. Least concerns- Nanofoods or foods- These are digested or solubilized in the gastrointestinal tract.
2. Moderate concern- It includes Non- bio persistent nanomaterials in foods which are not digested but carried by gastrointestinal tract.
3. Major concerns- It is a concern about nanofoods that contains nano additives which are indigestible insoluble and bio persistent.

• EFFECTS OF NANOTOXICITY

The important mechanism of nanotoxicity is the generation of reactive oxygen species i.e. ROS. The overproduction of ROS can cause oxidative stress and cells fails to maintain normal physiological functions. Nanotoxicity can also lead to DNA damage and can initiate cancer. When the humans are expose to nanomaterials, the cells allow them to pass through the cell membrane. Then nanoparticles affect the functions of cells. Many of the nanoparticles are commercially synthesized like iron oxide, zinc oxide nanoparticles having commercial application such as personal skin and hair repair products, coatings, paints etc. Nano zinc oxide and nano titanium oxides which are produced commercially causes major harmful effects to human health.

IX. CONCLUSION

Nanotechnology is becoming increasingly important in the food sector for preservation of fruits and vegetables and in packaging of fruits and vegetables. The application of nanotechnology are already being developed in food packaging and food safety. The incorporation of the nanomaterial in packaging of fruit and vegetables increases the barrier property of packaging against the oxygen, water vapour, invasion of microorganisms in fruits and vegetables. Edible nanocoatings find application in the fresh fruit and vegetable, where they might protect from moisture, gases, off-flavour and odor. Nanotechnology application utilized to determine the condition of fruit and vegetable in packaging by the help of nanosensors. Nanosensors are helpful to reduce the foodborne illness which is useful to maintain the food safety. Active packaging of fruits and vegetables used to change the condition of food product inside the packaging. Antimicrobial nanosensors incorporate into packaging so that packaging itself acts as antimicrobial. Nanotechnology is utilized to design nutraceutical and nutritional supplements. Nanoencapsulation contains nanosize ingredients and it is used to enhance the taste, flavor and shelf life of product. Nanotechnology improves the production and processing techniques and modification of colour, texture and sensation. In its widest sense, nanotechnology is a part of natural food processing and conventional food because characteristic property of many food relies on nanometer size components. Nanotechnology has an adverse effect in manufacturing, health, pharmaceutical industry and it causes risk to the environment. As development in nanotechnology continues to emerge, its applicability to food industry will increase potentially.

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